

DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE ENGINEERS' KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION AND PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY DESIGN SKILLS

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Abstract: New conceptual approaches are presented that direct the future engineer to acquire knowledge and develop the skills of designing a professional activity model in the higher education system. To date, it has been considered to provide integrated services for the remaining industries in the oil and gas industry.

Key words: Engineer, professional activity, specialized sciences, information technology, professional competence.

To effectively organize the educational process in educational institutions, to form and evaluate integral and systematic integrative knowledge, skills and qualifications of learners in order to ensure the implementation of priority tasks such as "Developing mechanisms for evaluating the quality of education, increasing the availability and efficiency of educational services" for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. becomes important. From this point of view , it is necessary to study the state of preparation of future engineers for professional activity, to research their professional competence in the relevant fields of specialization , to develop innovative pedagogical and diagnostic methods and to put them into practice .

In the pedagogical theory, certain factors have emerged to consider the professional training of the pedagogue, readiness for self-improvement. The analysis of scientific studies shows that the issue of preparing an engineer for self-improvement is comprehensively developed. Including, in the pedagogical theory, certain bases have been formed for studying the teacher's professional preparation for self-improvement. N.V. Kuzmina, V.A. Slastyonin identified the pedagogical factors of interaction between the teacher and the student in the situation of cooperation, in the creative educational environment, for the successful mobilization of the creative person in the professional activity. Intensification of education in higher educational institutions and application of pedagogical and information technologies to the educational process by the scientists of our country A.Abdukadirov, N.N.Azizkhodjaeva, U.Sh. Begimkulov, U.K. Tolipov, N.S. Sayidakhmetov, E.R. Yuzlikaev studies have been carried out.

According to international experience, deepening the organic connection of natural-scientific, social and technical sciences, science and production structures has a positive effect on educational efficiency. In particular, further expansion of the educational function on the basis of ensuring the harmony and mutual unity

of the elements of educational work in the further development of the trend of the theory and practice of professional pedagogy (integrative functions of education); innovative educational methods (integrative educational forms and methods); modernization of education (integrative technologies); integration processes such as educational outcome (integrity of personal and professional qualities) are important. This requires the preparation of future vocational education teachers for professional activity based on the integration of pedagogical and technical knowledge, the testing of educational results with diagnostic methods, the development of appropriate methodological recommendations for identified problems, and the expansion of the didactic capabilities of the integration of vocational education .

In the higher education system, the need to develop new conceptual approaches that direct the future engineer to acquire knowledge and develop the skills of designing a professional activity model is sharply placed on the agenda in the current globalization conditions. Including:

- specialization of future engineers in the teaching of practical training, the methodology of preparation for engineering activity, to help students actively acquire knowledge in the field of professional activity, to further improve their aesthetic worldviews, and on this basis, to support the formation of scientific worldviews, hard work, humanitarian skills of future engineers;

- To help future engineers to become mature engineers of the students of the "Oil and Gas Industry Technology" course and clearly understand the obligations to perceive and follow the laws of reality, things and events, procedures of socio-economic development, duty, responsibility based on the laws of beauty and moral integrity. ;

- they help ensure that future engineers are scientifically prepared for social-political, spiritual-ethical life, work, and in-depth mastering of scientific knowledge, skills and qualifications in the content of sciences.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that in improving the methodology of preparing the results of mastering future engineers for engineering activities, researching the methodology of preparing lessons for engineering activities among students of the "Oil and Gas Chemical Industry Technology" direction is one of the urgent pedagogical problems that are waiting for their solution.

REFERENCES:

1. E. Raynert Kak, rich countries are still rich, and poor countries remain poor. (2011), M.: Izd. Dom Gos. University of Economics - University of Economics.

2. Blaug M. Zakon sravnitelnyx preimushchestv // Ekonomicheskaya mysl v retrospective = Economic Theory in Retrospect . — M.: Delo, 1994. — S. 111-115. — XVII, 627 p. — ISBN 5-86461-151-4 4.
3. Zabelina O. Rossiyskaya spetsifika "Dutch disease.- Voprosy ekonomiki, 2004 No. 1

